

The horizontal EM infinite line source in the
half-space(air) above the conducting subsurface(earth)
containing a parallel conducting circular cylinder.

Sydney H.Hall

Abstract

The 2-D electromagnetic E and H fields due to a horizontal infinite line source in air above and on the surface of a conducting halfspace are described in a series formulation derived from the addition theorem for the modified Bessel function, $K_n \cos(n\psi)$ of the second kind, Watson(1966). The theorem relates the primary field with $n = 0$ to the generalised $K_n \cos(n\psi)$ for the scattered wave. The fields for the scattered wave are then expressed in a series formulation for the application of the boundary conditions. The angle ψ being subtended at either the source or the receiver. This low frequency (400Hz) near field geophysical treatment with five subsurface conductivities indicative of metamorphic to sedimentary rocks with the application of boundary conditions at the interface leads to complex coefficient sets of 21 harmonics for the scattered and subsurface fields. The source above the surface with a surface profile centred on it is described. The convergence with harmonic order and dependence on the surface profile is illustrated. For the source on the surface the profile is centred on a buried cylinder of radius 20 metres at a depth of 250 metres and with five conductivities indicative of sulphide ore bodies. The scattered fields of the source image in the cylinder which vary with the receiver position are established by positioning the image geometrically. Application of the boundary conditions for E and H at the cylinder surface again lead to complex coefficient sets for the scattered field from the source and the internal field within the cylinder. The harmonic behaviour and convergence of the computed coefficients and the influence

of the interface position on the sets is also illustrated. Interface fields are illustrated for each configuration and whilst there is distinction in E_y, H_x, H_z for the conductivities of the subsurface there is none for the cylinder conductivities. However there is clear evidence in the field phasors for its influence.

Introduction

The electromagnetic (EM) 2-D problem of a dielectric or conducting cylinder in a conductive half-space with excitation from a parallel infinite line source has been extensively treated in the geophysical and EM literature. In practice the infinite line source has its application to the search for underground rail lines, tunnels and ore veins. For such geophysical applications it becomes a low frequency near field exercise, for example in the approximate case of plane wave excitation, the solution of the Helmholtz equation can be expressed in a series of rapidly convergent series of Bessel functions (Jones, 1986). For cylindrical waves, Wait and Spies (1971) in a quasistatic treatment obtained a solution consisting of Bessel functions of the second kind, of zero order for the primary field of the source and the scattered field of its image in the half-space. This together with a Green's function for the current in the cylinder was treated analytically in the complex domain for a line source on the half-space interface. Wait (1972) improved on this by introducing Z , the series impedance in order to make successive approximations for the cylinder current using the Green's function as the electrical field source

Parry and Ward (1971) gave a Fredholm integral representation for cylinders of arbitrary cross-section and Hohmann (1971) similarly developed an integral representation based on a cylinder decomposed into a cross-section of squares centred with equivalent line currents. A whole-space solution is given in Ward and Hohmann (1987) and numerical models by Hohmann (1987). For the half-space Howard (1972) introduced a mode match solution to a 2D Fredholm integral equation with results matching those of Wait and Spies (1971).

The series method of presenting the problem with the whole-space represented by a circular cylinder earth with the cylinder and line source offset from the centre was first given by D'Yakonov (1959) and Ogunade in (1981) used this method for magnetotelluric applications.

The series method developed here, utilizes the link between primary and reflected waves represented by the addition theorem for Bessel functions of the second kind. The derived E and

H field expressions are for a plane earth interface leading to coefficient sets which are functions of both the parameters and the variable coordinates.

The Whole-space

An infinite y -directed EM line source, current I , in a free-space of permittivity ϵ_0 , conductivity σ_0 and permeability μ_0 possesses the three rectangular electromagnetic field components E_y, H_x, H_z . It is well known that the primary field E_y component is for a harmonic source of angular frequency ω ,

$$E_y = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} K_0(\gamma_0 R) \quad (1)$$

where as in Figure(1), R is the distance from the line source to a field point and K_0 is the modified Bessel function of the second kind and of zero order. γ_0 is the propagation constant given by

$$\gamma_0^2 = j\omega\mu_0\sigma_0 - \omega^2\mu_0\epsilon_0$$

H_x and H_z from Maxwell's equation are the corresponding z and x derivatives of E_y . The primary field E_y is thus determined by the zero order cylindrical harmonic. From the addition theorem for K_0 , (Watson,1966,p361,2nd Ed.),

$$E_y = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \delta_m K_m(\gamma_0 r^>) I_m(\gamma_0 r^<) \cos m(\theta - \theta_s) \quad (2)$$

with (r, θ) as the polar coordinates of the observation point and (r_s, θ_s) the coordinates of the source I and where $r^> = \max(r_s, r)$ and $r^< = \min(r_s, r)$ with $\delta_m = 1$ if $m = 0$ and $\delta_m = 2$ if $m > 0$. This expansion consists of I and K, the first and second kinds of modified Bessel functions. Similarly the addition theorem gives for the general n th order harmonic,

$$K_n(\gamma_0 R) \cos(n\psi^<) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \delta_m K_{m+n}(\gamma_0 r^>) I_m(\gamma_0 r^<) \cos m(\theta - \theta_s) \quad (3)$$

For the angle ψ , the inequality

$$|\gamma_0 r^< \exp \pm j(\theta - \theta_s)| < |\gamma_0 r^>|$$

must hold.

With the introduction of the half-space or any other structure, scattered waves occur and the general expansion of equation (3) which maintains the link with the modified Bessel functions of both kinds indicates that $K_n(\gamma_0 R) \cos(n\psi^<)$ should be the basis for any expansion.

In Figure(1) the two situations for $r < r_s$ and $r > r_s$ are illustrated. Since the acute angle ψ is subtended by $\min(r_s, r)$, the angle ψ at the field point when $r_s < r$ becomes the angle subtended at the source when $r < r_s$. The comparison between Equation(2) and (1) leads to the conclusion that $E_y(R, \psi; \gamma_0) = E_y(r, r_s, \theta, \theta_s; \gamma_0)$ so that the addition theorem can be regarded in effect as an equation of transformation. It is convenient to call the triangles depicted in Figure(1) as triangles of propagation-formed by the origin O , the source, I and the field point, P .

The source above the half-space

In Figure(2) the plane interface separates medium 0 (air) with parameters $\epsilon_0, \mu_0, \sigma_0$ from medium 1 (earth) with parameters $\epsilon_0, \mu_0, \sigma_1$ and the source I in medium 0, height H above the interface, produces an image $-I$ depth H below the interface. The origin of rectangular coordinates is at depth d below the interface and x_0 -directed distance x_0 from the source. The rays here are depicted in a schematic fashion to illustrate the primary ray (p), the reflected or scattered ray (s) and the transmitted ray (t) to the subsurface. We can write the E_y components of the later two rays as a sum of cylindrical harmonics with unknown coefficients, which are assumed to be functions only of the parameters involved. Thus writing,

$$E_y^p = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} K_0(\gamma_0 R^+) \quad (4a)$$

$$E_y^s = \frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n K_n(\gamma_0 R^-) \cos(n\psi^-) \quad (4b)$$

$$E_y^t = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n K_n(\gamma_1 R^+) \cos(n\psi^+) \quad (4c)$$

Here $R^+ = \sqrt{(x_0 - x)^2 + (z - d + H)^2}$ and $R^- = \sqrt{(x_0 - x)^2 + (z - d - H)^2}$ and $\delta_n = 1$ for $n = 0$ and $\delta_n = 2$ for $n > 0$. The magnetic primary field components are correspondingly,

$$H_x^p = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \frac{z - d + H}{R^+} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R^+) \quad (5a)$$

$$H_z^p = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \frac{x_0 - x}{R^+} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R^+) \quad (5b)$$

and H_x^s and H_z^s for the scattered ray with source $-I$,

$$H_x^s = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n \left\{ \frac{z - d - H}{R^-} \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R^-) \cos n\psi^- - n K_n(\gamma_0 R^-) \sin n\psi^- \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial z} \right\} \quad (6a)$$

$$H_z^s = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n \left\{ -\frac{x_0 - x}{R^-} \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R^-) \cos n\psi^- - n K_n(\gamma_0 R^-) \sin n\psi^- \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial x} \right\} \quad (6b)$$

For the transmitted ray due to the source I ,

$$H_x^t = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n \left\{ \frac{z-d+H}{R^+} \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R^+) \cos n\psi^+ - n K_n(\gamma_1 R^+) \sin n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial z} \right\} \quad (7a)$$

$$H_z^t = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n \left\{ -\frac{x_0-x}{R^+} \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R^+) \cos n\psi^+ - n K_n(\gamma_1 R^+) \sin n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial x} \right\} \quad (7b)$$

Where the prime $'$ denotes differentiation with respect to the argument.

In keeping with the requirement that ψ be an acute angle, ψ^+ , based on the $+I$ propagation triangle and ψ^- based on the image propagation triangle can be subtended at either the source or the field point according as $r_s < r$ or $r < r_s$.

At the interface of the half-space as shown in Figure(2), the primary field components, equations (4a),(5a),(6a) become with $z = d$ and $R = R^+ = R^-$.

$$E_y^p = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} K_0(\gamma_0 R) \quad (8a)$$

$$H_x^p = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \frac{H}{R} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R) \quad (8b)$$

$$H_z^p = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \frac{x_0-x}{R} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R) \quad (8c)$$

and for the scattered fields,

$$E_y^s = \frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n K_n(\gamma_0 R) \cos n\psi^- \quad (9a)$$

$$H_x^s = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n \left\{ \frac{H}{R} \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R) \cos n\psi^- + n K_n(\gamma_0 R) \sin n\psi^- \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial z} \right\} \quad (9b)$$

$$H_z^s = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n \left\{ \frac{x_0-x}{R} \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R) \cos n\psi^- + n K_n(\gamma_0 R) \sin n\psi^- \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial x} \right\} \quad (9c)$$

For the subsurface fields the components are,

$$E_y^t = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n K_n(\gamma_1 R) \cos n\psi^+ \quad (10a)$$

$$H_x^t = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n \left\{ \frac{H}{R} \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R) \cos n\psi^+ - n K_n(\gamma_1 R) \sin n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial z} \right\} \quad (10b)$$

$$H_z^t = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n \left\{ \frac{x_0-x}{R} \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R) \cos n\psi^+ + n K_n(\gamma_1 R) \sin n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial x} \right\} \quad (10c)$$

where the x and z derivatives of ψ^+ and ψ^- are described in Appendix A.

At the interface, the boundary conditions give for E_y and H_x

$$E_y^p(R; \gamma_0) + E_y^s(R, \psi^-; \gamma_0) = E_y^t(R, \psi^+; \gamma_1) \quad (11a)$$

$$H_x^p(R; \gamma_0) + H_x^s(R, \psi^-; \gamma_0) = H_x^t(R, \psi^+; \gamma_1) \quad (11b)$$

and since free-space permeability is assumed throughout, then

$$H_z^p(R; \gamma_0) + H_z^s(R, \psi^-; \gamma_0) = H_z^t(R, \psi^+; \gamma_1) \quad (11c)$$

On substituting equations (8),(9),(10) in equations(11) the two sets of coefficients A_n and B_n are obtained. For the expansion of the primary field both the Neumann series expansion of K_0 (Ambramovitz & Stegun,1965) and the addition theorem with their derivatives when jointly used provided in their agreement the authenticity of the coding. From E_y and H_x the $n = 0$ coefficients were,

$$A_0 = -\left\{ \ln\left(\frac{\gamma_0 R}{2}\right) + \Gamma \right\} \left\{ \gamma_1 K_0'(\gamma_1 R) I_0(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 K_0(\gamma_1 R) I_0'(\gamma_0 R) \right\} - \gamma_0 I_0'(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R) \\ + \frac{1}{R} I_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_1 R) \quad (12a)$$

$$B_0 = \left\{ \ln\left(\frac{\gamma_0 R}{2}\right) + \Gamma \right\} \left\{ \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R) I_0(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 I_0'(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R) \right\} + \gamma_0 I_0'(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R) \\ - \frac{1}{R} I_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R) \quad (12b)$$

$$\gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_1 R) + \gamma_1 K_0'(\gamma_1 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R)$$

and for $n > 0$

$$A_n = (H/R) \left\{ \frac{\gamma_1}{n} K_n'(\gamma_1 R) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) + \gamma_0 \left(\frac{1+2n}{n(1+n)} \right) I_{2n+1}(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R) \right\} \cos n\psi^+ \\ - K_n(\gamma_1 R) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) \sin n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial z} \quad (13a)$$

$$H/R \left\{ \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R) + \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R) \right\} \cos n\psi^- \cos n\psi^+ \\ - n K_n(\gamma_1 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R) \left\{ \sin n\psi^+ \cos n\psi^- \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial z} + \sin n\psi^- \cos n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial z} \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_n = (H/R) \left\{ \frac{\gamma_0}{n} K'_n(\gamma_0 R) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 \left(\frac{1+2n}{n(1+n)} \right) I_{2n+1}(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R) \right\} \cos n\psi^- \\
- \sin n\psi^- K_n(\gamma_0 R) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial z}
\end{aligned} \tag{13b}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(H/R) \left\{ \gamma_0 K'_n(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R) + \gamma_1 K'_n(\gamma_1 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R) \right\} \cos n\psi^- \cos \psi^+ \\
- n K_n(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R) \left\{ \sin n\psi^- \cos n\psi^+ \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial z} + \sin n\psi^+ \cos n\psi^- \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial z} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

where Γ is the Euler constant.

Computing the half-space coefficients and fields

As suitable low frequency near field parameters for computing Equations (12,13) a 400 Hertz source was used, x-axis distance $x_0=1500\text{m}$ with height above the interface $H=150\text{m}$ and origin of coordinates $d=250\text{m}$ below (Figure (2)). For the conducting subsurface a range of five skin depths were chosen with a range of 100,250,500,750,1000m. A_n and B_n ($n=0,20$) coefficients were determined as phasors for each of the 101 interface field points over the x-axis range $-1000,+1000\text{m}$.

Routines used for evaluating the Modified Bessel functions were MCIKNA and MCIKNB available from the University of Illinois website and an MBF routine. The former evaluate higher orders by recurrence whilst the MBF routine was developed from the basic and asymptotic (large order and large argument) equations of Abramowitz & Stegun (1972).

All plots of complex coefficients and fields are presented as composites of $\log(\text{modulus})$ and phase.

The convergence with order of the coefficients as abscissa is demonstrated in Figures(3,4) for A_n and B_n respectively, with the coefficients as the average of the 101 field points. As phasors Figures(3a) and (4a) show the modulus on the natural logarithmic scale and Figures(3b) and (4b) the accumulated phase in radians of A_n and B_n for $n=0$ to $n=20$ for the skin depths numbered 1-5 in order of increasing skin depth. There is no distinction between skin depths for the A_n coefficients but it is clearly evident for B_n .

The range of the ordinates in all plots is based on the maximum and minimum of the data so that in this case the A_n logarithmic modulus decreases by -450 and the B_n modulus by -350. The actual decrease in modulus is 2.0×10^9 per order for A_n and 4.49×10^7 per order for

B_n . The corresponding accumulated phase for the 21 coefficient orders is 30 radians for A_n and 60 for B_n

The x-axis dependence of the coefficients computed for each field point is illustrated by the plots of Figures(5) and (6) for A_n and B_n respectively. The example shown is for the skin depth of 100m and in each case for the larger skin depths there was linearity on the logarithmic scale for the initial orders but less so with increasing order. The numbers in the plots indicate the order of the harmonic. For the phase, linearity is evident for the A_n coefficients, Figure(5b) but not for B_n in Figure(6b). In general there is a distinction between even and odd harmonics of the phase particularly for A_n with succeeding orders differing in phase by multiples of $\pi/2$ but in B_n alternative phase changes of $+\pi/2 - \pi/2$ extending over the orders 0–9 are apparent.

The error in the equality of the fields in mediums 0 and 1 at the interface were for E_y , equation (14), in the range $-20 \rightarrow -15$ for logarithmic modulus and $-1.5 \rightarrow 3.0$ radians in phase for the 100m skin depth and 0.0 radians for the remaining skin depths. For comparison the range in logarithmic modulus of E_y is $-9.5 \rightarrow -6.0$ and $0.8 \rightarrow 1.2$ radians for phase.

$$E_y^{err} = E_y^p + E_y^s - E_y^t \quad (14)$$

Similarly the 100m skin depth determined the range of error in H_x , $-35 \rightarrow -23$ in logarithmic modulus and $-2.5 \rightarrow 3.0$ radians in phase for the 100m skin depth and 0.0 radians in phase for the other 4 skin depths. The comparison is the H_x field of Figure (8). The sub-source point determined the errors in H_z with a range of $-22 \rightarrow -19$ in logarithmic modulus and $-\pi \rightarrow +\pi$ in phase. The comparison is with Figure(9).

Figures(7,8,9) are interface plots of the surface and subsurface fields $E_y^0 = E_y^p + E_y^s$ and $E_y^1 = E_y^t$, and correspondingly for H_x^0 and H_x^1, H_z^0 and H_z^1 . No discrimination is apparent between these two sources of field with surface fields indicated by boxes and subsurface fields by circles. There is considerable discrimination with skin thickness displayed in the modulus of E_y and comparatively in phase, Figure(7) but although the phase in H_x exhibits the influence of the source image the discrimination with skin depth in both modulus and phase is miniscule. The range for H_x , Figure(8) is -6.5 to -10.0 in log modulus and 0.005 to 0.035 radians in phase. The H_z fields, Figure(9), are delineated by the sharp minimum in modulus at the sub-source point with the range of -8 to -22 in logarithmic modulus and the peak of π radians in phase.

Δ -Skin depth(m), σ -Conductivity(S/m)					
Δ_1	100	250	500	750	1000
σ_1	0.0633	0.0101	0.0025	0.0011	0.0006
Δ_2	0.2516	0.7958	2.516	7.958	15.915
σ_2	10,000	1000	100	10	2.5

Table 1: Skin depths and conductivities for half-space(1) and cylinder(2).

Source on the interface and the circular cylinder

With the source on the interface $R = x_0 - x$ and $H = 0$, Figure(10). When $r \leq r_s$, $\psi = \tan^{-1} \frac{x_0}{d}$, a constant angle subtended at the source but when $r > r_s$, $\psi = \tan^{-1} \frac{d}{x}$. By the same procedure for deriving the A_n and B_n coefficients of equations (12 & 13), using E_y and H_z , we have for $n = 0$,

$$A_0 = \frac{-\left\{\ln\left(\frac{\gamma_0 R}{2}\right) + \Gamma\right\} \left\{\gamma_1 K'_0(\gamma_1 R) I_0(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 I'_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_1 R)\right\} - K_0(\gamma_1 R) I_0(\gamma_0 R) / (x_0 - x)}{\gamma_1 K'_0(\gamma_1 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 K'_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_1 R)} \quad (15a)$$

$$B_0 = \frac{-\left\{\ln\left(\frac{\gamma_0 R}{2}\right) + \Gamma\right\} \left\{\gamma_0 K'_0(\gamma_0 R) I_0(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 I'_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R)\right\} - I_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R) / (x_0 - x)}{\gamma_0 K'_0(\gamma_0 R) K_0(\gamma_1 R) - \gamma_1 K'_0(\gamma_1 R) K_0(\gamma_0 R)} \quad (15b)$$

and for $n > 0$

$$A_n = \frac{\left\{\gamma_1 K'_n(\gamma_1 R) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 I'_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R)\right\} \cos(n\psi) / n + I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R) \sin(n\psi) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}}{\left\{\gamma_1 K'_n(\gamma_1 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 K'_n(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R)\right\} \cos^2(n\psi)} \quad (16a)$$

$$B_n = \frac{\left\{\gamma_0 K'_n(\gamma_0 R) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) - \gamma_0 I'_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R)\right\} \cos(n\psi) / n + I_{2n}(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R) \sin(n\psi) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}}{\left\{\gamma_0 K'_n(\gamma_0 R) K_n(\gamma_1 R) - \gamma_1 K'_n(\gamma_1 R) K_n(\gamma_0 R)\right\} \cos^2(n\psi)} \quad (16b)$$

On the interface, Figure(10), the x-axis surface profile is $-1000, +1000m$ centred on the cylinder at a depth of 250m with the line source at $x = +1500m$. The decrease in logarithmic modulus with order n of the average A_n coefficients of equations(15a) and 16a), Figure(11a), is -400 for the 21 coefficients with no evidence of distinction between the five skin depths. Similarly there is no distinction in the accumulated phase of -30 radians evident in Figure(11b). For

the average Bn coefficients of equations (15b) and (16b), the decrease is -350 in logarithmic modulus,(Figure 12a) and there is clear distinction between the five skin depths. Similarly there is distinction with the accumulated phase of 60 radians,Figure (12b).

The An coefficients dependence on the x-axis range is illustrated in the example for a 100m skin depth,(Figure13). In Figure(13a) for the logarithmic modulus there is independence for order 0 but dependence increasing to 100 at order 20. In Figure (13b) the A_n phase is constant for all orders and the difference between successive phases is an odd multiple of $\pi/2$.For the Bn coefficients, Figure (14a), the dependence in modulus at order 0 is approximately 2 orders of magnitude over the x-axis range increasing to 100 at $n = 20$.For the phase,Figure(14b),there is an overall decrease of 25 radians with a difference of π radians between succeeding orders

The phasor errors in log modulus for the equality of the fields at the surface of the half-space for E_y, H_x, H_z ranged over $-26 \rightarrow -22$ for $E_y, -58 \rightarrow -40$ for H_x and $-21 \rightarrow -16$ for H_z . The error range in log modulus for H_x , indicated an extremely small vector as can be expected with consequent random errors in phase, the phase errors for E_y were $-2.0 \rightarrow 2.5$ radians while the phase errors for H_z were $0.8 \rightarrow 1.0$ radians.The comparison is with the corresponding fields at the interface,Figures(15),(16),(17) respectively.

There is no distinction between the two E_y fields over the profile range at the interface , Figure(15), but clear demarcation between the five skin depths in both modulus and phase. The rectangular boxes refer to the Ey0 field and the circles refer to the Ey1. In Figure(16), for H_x^0 and H_x^1 ,there is no distinction between the fields and the skin depths in the log modulus of H_x and the range in phase is virtually zero.The demarcation for skin depth is not so prominent for Hz in both modulus and phase,Figure(17), since the range in phase is $0.05 \rightarrow 0.035$ radians compared with 0.25 radians for the phase of Ey.

The conducting cylinder of radius $a = 25m$, centred at the origin with propagation constant γ_2 ,Figure(10), produces a reflected wave together with a wave from the interior line current distribution induced by the source I . The image I' of the source in the cylinder is found by constructing the tangent at Q the point of reflection, as in Figure(10), drawing the bisector KQ of the angle subtended by PI at Q and I' is located on the intersection of the projection of PQ to the line drawn parallel to KQ from the source I , Trappeniers et al.(2006). In actuality there is a second reflection with the diametrically opposite face of the cylinder. This image is neglected in the following treatment since its effect will be considerably reduced by the loss of energy through the conducting cylinder as indicated by the skin depth and the increased path

length. It is also refracted towards r_b in the conducting interior but these considerations would not all apply if the cylinder was considered as a tunnel.

To determine the reflection angle α and the corresponding angle θ_t of the radius a to the point of reflection then from the bisected angle triangle PQI,

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_t &= \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\{\pi - (\theta + \beta_1) - (\theta_s - \beta_2)\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\{(\theta + \beta_1) + (\theta_s - \beta_2)\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\left\{\theta + \sin^{-1} \frac{a \sin(\theta - \theta_t)}{s_r} + \theta_s - \sin^{-1} \frac{a \sin(\theta_t - \theta_s)}{s_s}\right\}.\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

where

$$s_r^2 = r^2 + a^2 - 2ar \cos(\theta - \theta_t),$$

$$s_s^2 = r^2 + a^2 - 2ar_s \cos(\theta_t - \theta_s).$$

Equation (17) leads to

$$\begin{aligned}\sin\left\{\theta_t - \frac{1}{2}(\theta + \theta_s)\right\} &= \frac{a \sin(\theta - \theta_t)}{s_r} \sqrt{1 - \left\{\frac{a \sin(\theta_t - \theta_s)}{s_s}\right\}^2} \\ &\quad - \frac{a \sin(\theta_t - \theta_s)}{s_s} \sqrt{1 - \left\{\frac{a \sin(\theta - \theta_t)}{s_r}\right\}^2}\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

With θ_t the angle of reflection α is obtained from $\alpha = \theta_t - \theta_s + \beta_2$ and the distance $PI' = R_c$ from $R_c = s_r + s_s$ since the QII' is an isosceles triangle. Following Hohmann(1987) it is convenient to consider the equivalent problem of a cylinder with conductivity $\sigma_c = \sigma_2 - \sigma_1$ in a whole-space of conductivity σ_0 . Then to apply the boundary conditions at the point of reflection Q, the E and H fields in polar coordinates are, for the primary field,

$$E_y^p = -\frac{j\omega\mu I}{2\pi} K_0(\gamma_0 s_s) \quad (19a)$$

$$H_r^p = \frac{I}{2\pi} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 s_s) \frac{\partial s_s}{r \partial \theta}, \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (19b)$$

$$H_\theta^p = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 s_s) \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r}, \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (19c)$$

and for the scattered field,

$$E_y^s = \frac{j\omega\mu I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n C_n K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) \cos n\psi_c, \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (20a)$$

$$H_r^s = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n C_n \left\{ \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 s_c) \frac{\partial s_c}{r \partial \theta} \cos n\psi_c - n K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{r \partial \theta} \right\}, \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (20b)$$

$$H_\theta^s = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n C_n \left\{ \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 s_c) \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} \cos n\psi_c - n K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{\partial r} \right\}, \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (20c)$$

and for the fields in the cylinder,

$$E_y^t = -\frac{j\omega\mu I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n D_n I_n(\gamma_c r), \quad (r = a) \quad (21a)$$

$$H_r^t = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n D_n \gamma_c I_n'(\gamma_c r) \frac{\partial r}{r \partial \theta}, \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (21b)$$

$$H_\theta^t = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n D_n \gamma_c I_n'(\gamma_c r), \quad (r = a, \theta = \theta_t) \quad (21c)$$

For the scattered fields from the cylinder the triangle of propagation is OQI', Figure(13), and the acute angle is, $\psi_c = \alpha$ if $r'_s < a$ or $\psi_c = QI'O = \beta_3$ if $a < r'_s$, i.e.

$$\alpha = \pi - \sin^{-1} \left\{ \frac{r'_s \sin(\theta_t - \theta_s)}{s_s} \right\}, \quad r'_s < a$$

$$\beta_3 = \sin^{-1} \left\{ \left(\frac{a}{r'_s} \right) \sin \alpha \right\}, \quad a < r'_s$$

Since a uniform concentric induced current system is implied, the H_r^t field at the boundary is zero so that H_θ^t is the relevant choice for the boundary condition. From the set of E_y^p, E_y^s, E_y^t and $H_\theta^p, H_\theta^s, H_\theta^t$, Equations(19-21), the C_n and D_n coefficients are, firstly for the zero order coefficients,

$$C_0 = \frac{\frac{1}{s_r} \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r} I_0(\gamma_0 s_s) I_0(\gamma_c a) - \left\{ \ln\left(\frac{\gamma_0 s_s}{2}\right) + \Gamma \right\} \left\{ \gamma_c I_0'(\gamma_c a) I_0(\gamma_0 s_s) - \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r} I_0'(\gamma_0 s_s) I_0(\gamma_c a) \right\}}{\gamma_c I_0'(\gamma_c a) K_0(\gamma_0 s_c) - \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} K_0'(\gamma_0 s_c) I_0(\gamma_c a)} \quad (22)$$

and,

$$D_0 = -\frac{\frac{1}{s_s} \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r} I_0(\gamma_0 s_s) K_0(\gamma_0 s_c) + \left\{ \ln\left(\frac{\gamma_0 s_c}{2}\right) + \Gamma \right\} \left\{ \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} K_0'(\gamma_0 s_c) I_0(\gamma_0 s_s) - \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r} I_0'(\gamma_0 s_s) K_0(\gamma_0 s_c) \right\}}{\gamma_c I_0'(\gamma_c a) K_0(\gamma_0 s_c) - \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} K_0'(\gamma_0 s_c) I_0(\gamma_c a)} \quad (23)$$

and for the subsequent orders,

$$C_n = \frac{\frac{\gamma_c}{n} I_n'(\gamma_c a) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 s_c) - \frac{\gamma_0}{n} \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r} I_{2n}'(\gamma_0 s_s) I_n(\gamma_c a)}{\left\{ \gamma_c I_n'(\gamma_c a) K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) - \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} K_n'(\gamma_0 s_c) I_n(\gamma_c a) \right\} \cos n\psi_c + n K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) I_n(\gamma_c a) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{\partial r}}$$

(24)

$$D_n = \frac{\frac{\gamma_0}{n} \left\{ \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} K'_n(\gamma_0 s_c) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 s_s) - \frac{\partial s_s}{\partial r} I'_{2n}(\gamma_0 s_s) K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) \right\} \cos n\psi_c - K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) I_{2n}(\gamma_0 s_s) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{\partial r}}{\left\{ \gamma_0 \frac{\partial s_c}{\partial r} K'_n(\gamma_0 s_c) I_n(\gamma_c a) - \gamma_c I'_n(\gamma_c a) K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) \right\} \cos n\psi_c - n K_n(\gamma_0 s_c) I_n(\gamma_c a) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{\partial r}} \quad (25)$$

An essential partial differential occurring in that of α, s_c, s_s is $\frac{\partial \theta_t}{\partial r}$. From the bisected triangle PQI, where $s_c = s_s$ this reduces at $r = a, \theta = \theta_t$ to,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \theta_t}{\partial r} \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{r_b - a}{s_r} \right\} \cos \theta_t \right] / \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_b^2}{s_r^2} \sin^2 \theta_t} - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{a - r_b}{s_s} \cos \theta_t + \frac{a r_s r_b}{s_s^3} \sin \theta_t \sin(\theta_t - \theta_s) \right\} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_b^2}{s_s^2} \sin^2 \theta_t} \\ = \frac{1}{2} a \sin \theta_t \left[\frac{1}{s_r} \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_b^2}{s_r^2} \sin^2 \theta_t} - \frac{1}{s_s} \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_b^2}{s_s^2} \sin^2 \theta_t} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Computing the cylinder coefficients and surface fields

The convergence with harmonic order of the C_n and D_n coefficients for the half-space skin depth of 100m and the five skin depths in the cylinder, Table(1), is shown in the plots of Figures (18) and (19) respectively. The coefficient phasors are averaged over the 101 field points and plotted with the order as abscissa. For the 21 coefficients the natural logarithm of the modulus of C_n in Figure(18a) decreases by -450 and accumulates to 30 radians, (Figure(18b)). In actuality the modulus decreases by 2.0×10^9 per order. The convergence of the D_n coefficients, Figure(19a) is -400 in logarithmic modulus and an accumulation of 65 radians in phase, (Figure(19b)). Again in real terms the decrease in modulus is 1.86×10^8 per order. There is clear distinction in the D_n averages for the 5 skin depths in the cylinder but there is no graphical distinction for the C_n coefficients. Plots for the remaining half-space skin depths revealed the same characteristics.

The individual phasors of the C_n and D_n coefficients for the half-space skin depth of 100m and with the skin depth in the cylinder of 0.2516m versus the field points of the half-space interface are shown in Figures(20) and (21). The independence of the x-axis field points is evident in the linearity in each of C_n and D_n in both log modulus and phase. This linearity was repeated with other combinations of the two sets of skin depths of Table(1). For the phase of C_n , Figure (20b) there is a difference of $\pi/2$ or $3\pi/2$ between successive orders whilst for D_n , Figure(21b), the separation between successive orders is π .

The errors in the equality of $E_y^p + E_y^s$ and E_y^t and $H_\theta^p + H_\theta^s$ and H_θ^t , equations (19-21), at the cylinder boundary for the 100m skin depth in the subsurface and the five skin depths in the

$\sigma_1 \downarrow \sigma_2 \rightarrow$	10000	1000	100	10	2.5
0.063	10000	999.9	99.94	9.937	2.437
0.0101	10000	1000	99.99	9.990	2.490
0.0025	10000	1000	100.0	9.927	2.497
0.0011	10000	1000	100.0	9.999	2.499
0.0006	10000	1000	100.0	10.00	2.490

Table 2: σ_c conductivities(S/m) for the cylinder.

cylinder were, for the natural logarithmic modulus of E_y , in the range $0.3 \times 10^{-11} \rightarrow 1.3 \times 10^{-11}$ with a phase error of $0.6 \rightarrow 1.5$ radians. For H_θ the corresponding errors were $2.6 \times 10^{-15} \rightarrow 2.5 \times 10^{-10}$ and for the phase $-3.0 \rightarrow +3.0$ radians. The comparison is with Figures(22) and (23).

In Figure(22) the exterior field $E_y^p + E_y^s$ and the interior field E_y^t on the cylinder boundary, for the half-space skin depth of 100m demonstrates the extent of fit. The x-axis profile is used as abscissa in place of the corresponding points of reflection. In the logarithmic modulus and the phase, the fit improves with increasing skin depth in the cylinder. The corresponding plot for H_θ , Figure(23), shows that the two fields are almost identical for all five skin depths in the cylinder with a logarithmic modulus range of the order of $-15 \rightarrow -23$ and -0.088 to -0.095 radians in phase.

Combined fields at the interface

The primary E and H fields at the half-space interface are, with $R = x_0 - x$

$$E_y^p = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} K_0(\gamma_0 R) \quad (27a)$$

$$H_r^p = \frac{I}{2\pi} \gamma_0 K_0'(\gamma_0 R) \frac{\partial R}{r \partial \theta} \quad (27b)$$

$$H_\theta^p = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R) \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} \quad (27c)$$

and the transmitted fields in the subsurface,

$$E_y^t = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n K_n(\gamma_1 R) \cos n\psi \quad (27d)$$

$$H_r^t = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n \left\{ \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R) \cos n\psi \frac{\partial R}{r \partial \theta} - n K_n(\gamma_1 R) \sin n\psi \frac{\partial \psi}{r \partial \theta} \right\} \quad (27e)$$

$$H_\theta^t = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n B_n \left\{ \gamma_1 K_n'(\gamma_1 R) \cos n\psi \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} - n K_n(\gamma_1 R) \sin n\psi \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \right\} \quad (27f)$$

The scattered E and H fields for the image $-I$ of the source in the half-space are,

$$E_y^s = \frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n K_n(\gamma_0 R) \cos n\psi \quad (28a)$$

$$H_r^s = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n \left\{ \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R) \cos n\psi \frac{\partial R}{r \partial \theta} - n K_n(\gamma_0 R) \sin n\psi \frac{\partial \psi}{r \partial \theta} \right\} \quad (28b)$$

$$H_\theta^s = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n A_n \left\{ \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R) \cos n\psi \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} - n K_n(\gamma_0 R) \sin(n\psi) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \right\} \quad (28c)$$

$$\psi = \theta_s, r \leq r_s = \theta, r > r_s, x > 0 = \pi - \theta, x \leq 0$$

and the scattered fields from the source $-I'$ in the cylinder are,

$${}_c E_y^s = \frac{j\omega\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n C_n K_n(\gamma_0 R_{sc}) \cos n\psi_c \quad (29a)$$

$${}_c H_r^s = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n C_n \left\{ \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R_{sc}) \frac{\partial R_{sc}}{r \partial \theta} \cos n\psi_c - n K_n(\gamma_0 R_{sc}) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{r \partial \theta} \right\} \quad (29b)$$

$${}_c H_\theta^s = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n C_n \left\{ \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 R_{sc}) \frac{\partial R_{sc}}{\partial r} \cos n\psi_c - n K_n(\gamma_0 R_{sc}) \sin n\psi_c \frac{\partial \psi_c}{\partial r} \right\} \quad (29c)$$

Where $R_{sc} = s_r + s_c$ and $\psi_c = \beta_1$ when $r'_s \leq r$ or $\psi_c = \beta_3$ when $r \leq r'_s$, (Figure(10)).

Finally for the transmitted fields from the cylinder,

$${}_c E_y^t = -\frac{j\omega\mu_0}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n D_n K_n(\gamma_0 r) \frac{I_n(\gamma_c a)}{K_n(\gamma_0 a)} \quad (30a)$$

$${}_c H_r^t = \frac{I}{2\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta_n D_n \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 r) \frac{\gamma_c}{\gamma_0} \frac{I_n'(\gamma_c a)}{K_n'(\gamma_0 a)} \frac{\partial r}{r \partial \theta} \quad (31b)$$

$${}_c H_\theta^t = -\frac{I}{2\pi} \delta_n D_n \gamma_0 K_n'(\gamma_0 r) \frac{\gamma_c}{\gamma_0} \frac{I_n'(\gamma_c a)}{K_n'(\gamma_0 a)} \quad (30c)$$

The total fields at the half-space interface in E_y , i.e.,

$$E_y^0 = E_y^p + E_y^s + {}_c E_y^s - {}_c E_y^t$$

$$E_y^1 = E_y^t + {}_c E_y^s - {}_c E_y^t$$

and correspondingly the fields of H_r and H_θ at the halfspace interface on conversion to H_x and H_z are plotted in Figures(24),(25),(26). These illustrate the the specific case of the five skin depths in the half-space with the cylinder skin depth of 0.2516m. As with the E_y, H_x, H_z fields of Figures(15),(16) and (17) the profile is the x-axis range of $-1000 \rightarrow +1000m$ centred on the cylinder. In E_y , Figure(24), the influence of the cylinder is evident particularly in the modulus rather than the phase as the latter range is 0.05 radian. In H_x , Figure(25), the anomaly is essentially the effect of the cylinder, though small, as the range of the logarithmic modulus is $-11.0 \rightarrow -9.4$ and the phase range is $-3.5 \times 10^{-4} \rightarrow -1.5 \times 10^{-4}$. H_z in Figure(26) displays the characteristic maximum and minimum centred on the cylinder in both modulus and phase.

Conclusions

The electromagnetic problem of the y-directed infinite line source in the air above and on the interface of the conductive earth half-space which includes a parallel conductive circular cylinder is developed as a low frequency (400 Hertz) near field problem amenable to a series treatment. The E_y, H_x, H_z field components for the incident, scattered, and transmitted waves are formulated on the basis of the addition theorem for modified Bessel functions of the second kind $K_n(\gamma R) \cos(n\psi)$ with order n . By this means the addition theorem relationship for the primary field, $n = 0$ is maintained for the scattered and transmitted waves when formulated in their series expressions for $n \geq 0$. The angle ψ is subtended at either the source image or the receiver for the half-space and similarly for the cylinder. The location of the source image in the cylinder, is determined geometrically and its position varies with the receiver point on the half-space. This treatment thus differs from the customary practice of using the angle subtended at the origin of coordinates.

D'Yakonov(1959) and Ogunade(1981) employed a cylindrical earth parallel to the line source in order to eliminate any effect on their series coefficients by an x-axis profile. This method employs a plane earth interface and the consequence for x-axis profiling is a dependence which is minimal for $n = 0$ and increases with order. Its influence was mitigated by computing individual A_n and B_n half-space coefficient sets for each profile point. This effect is absent from the C_n and D_n cylinder coefficients.

The linear convergence with order of the x-axis averaged A_n and B_n coefficients in the logarithmic scale for the modulus and for the accumulated phase is certainly adequate to

determine the E and H fields for the half-space. Similarly the averaged C_n and D_n cylinder coefficients for the cylinder in the conducting half-space are adequately convergent with order and sufficient to determine the E and H cylinder fields. The conclusion is that for the scattered and transmitted waves the harmonics of the coefficients contribute in a regular decrease in the natural logarithmic scale and a similar regular increase in the accumulated phase.

For the five half-space skin depths and the skin depth in the cylinder of 0.2516m the total E_y, H_x, H_z fields of the half-space with cylinder on comparison with the half-space corresponding fields with no cylinder indicated the anomaly produced by the cylinder. All components displayed the characteristic shape of the anomaly although for E_y and H_x the x-axis range is insufficient to completely delineate the anomaly. In the H_x field there was no credible response from the half-space in both the logarithmic modulus and phase whereas with the cylinder present the entire H_x response was due to the cylinder. The horizontal extent of the H_x anomaly was large but the range of logarithmic modulus and phase indicated a small response. The ranges in logarithmic modulus and phase for H_z with and without the cylinder were comparable and the anomaly, as a considerable proportion of both these ranges, is clearly evident.

Acknowledgments

My grateful thanks to my wife for tolerating with unending patience my addiction to this work and to the Rev. Canon John Morgan for his brilliant literary research in the Cambridge library archives. I also owe grateful thanks to Dr. S.J Hearn for his skill in the final preparation of this manuscript.

References

- D'Yakonov, B.P., 1959, The diffraction of electromagnetic waves by a circular cylinder in a homogeneous half-space, *Izvestiya, Acad. Sci., U.S.S.R., Geophys. ser. no.* **9**, 950-955.
- Hohmann, G.W., 1987 in "Electromagnetic methods in applied geophysics-Theory", v.1, Society of Exploration Geophysicists, Tulsa Oklahoma, USA.
- Howard, Allen Q., Jr. 1972. The electromagnetic fields of a subterranean cylindrical inhomogeneity excited by a line source. *Geophysics*, **37**, 975-984.
- Jones, D.S., 1986, "Acoustic and Electromagnetic Waves", Oxford Science Publications, Clarendon Press, Oxford, ISBN 0-19-853365-9.
- Ogunade, S.O., 1981, Electromagnetic response of an embedded cylinder for line current excitation, *Geophysics* **46**, 45-52.
- Parry, J.R. and Ward, S.H., 1971. Electromagnetic scattering from a cylinder of arbitrary cross-section in a conductive halfspace, *Geophysics*, **36**, 67-100.
- Trappeniers, P., Gonzalez, R.G., van Lil, E., van de Capelle, A., 2006, "Geometrical optics & electromagnetic models for cylindrical obstacles", *Progress in Electromagnetics Research*, Cambridge, USA, March 26-29, 495-504.
- Wait, J.R., Spies, Kenneth, P., 1971 Subsurface electromagnetic fields of a line source on a conducting half-space, **6** *Radio Science*, Nos. 8,9; 781-786.
- Wait, J.R., 1962, *Electromagnetic fields in stratified media*, New York, MacMillan
- Wait, J.R., 1972, The effect of a buried conductor on the subsurface fields for a line source excitation, *Radio Science*, **7**, 587-591.
- Ward, S.H., Hohmann, G.W., 1987, in "Electromagnetic methods in applied geophysics-Theory", v1, Society of Exploration Geophysics, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA.
- Watson, G.N., 1966, *Theory of Bessel Functions*, 2nd Ed., Cambridge University Press.

Appendix

From the acute angles ψ^+ and ψ^- of the propagation triangles POI^+ and POI^- of Figure (2), the application of the sine law leads to the following ψ derivatives with respect to x and z , for $r < r_s^- < r_s^+$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^+}{\partial x} = \left\{x - R^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial x} + r_s^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial x} \cos(\psi^+)\right\} / r_s^+ R^+ \sin(\psi^+) \quad (A1)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^+}{\partial z} = \left\{d - R^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial z} + r_s^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial z} \cos(\psi^+)\right\} / r_s^+ R^+ \sin(\psi^+) \quad (A2)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^-}{\partial x} = \left\{x - R^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial x} + r_s^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial x} \cos(\psi^-)\right\} / r_s^- R^- \sin(\psi^-) \quad (A3)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^-}{\partial z} = \left\{d - R^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial z} + r_s^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial z} \cos(\psi^-)\right\} / r_s^- R^- \sin(\psi^-) \quad (A4)$$

for $r_s^- < r < r_s^+$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^+}{\partial x} = \left\{x - R^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial x} + r_s \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial x} \cos(\psi^+)\right\} / r_s^+ R^+ \sin(\psi^+) \quad (A5)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^+}{\partial z} = \left\{d - R^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial z} + r_s \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial z} \cos(\psi^+)\right\} / r_s^+ R^+ \sin(\psi^+) \quad (A6)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^-}{\partial x} = \left\{\left(R^- \frac{x}{r} + r \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial x}\right) \cos(\psi^-) - x - R^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial x}\right\} / r R^- \sin(\psi^-) \quad (A7)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^-}{\partial z} = \left\{\left(R^- \frac{d}{r} + r \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial z}\right) \cos(\psi^-) - d - R^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial z}\right\} / r R^- \sin(\psi^-) \quad (A8)$$

for $r_s^- < r_s^+ < r$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^+}{\partial x} = \left\{\left(R^+ \frac{x}{r} + r \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial x}\right) \cos(\psi^+) - x - R^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial x}\right\} / r R^+ \sin(\psi^+) \quad (A9)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^+}{\partial z} = \left\{\left(R^+ \frac{d}{r} + r \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial z}\right) \cos(\psi^+) - d - R^+ \frac{\partial R^+}{\partial z}\right\} / r R^+ \sin(\psi^+) \quad (A10)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^-}{\partial x} = \left\{\left(R^- \frac{x}{r} + r \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial x}\right) \cos(\psi^-) - x - R^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial x}\right\} / r R^- \sin(\psi^-) \quad (A11)$$

$$\frac{\partial\psi^-}{\partial z} = \left\{\left(R^- \frac{d}{r} + r \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial z}\right) \cos(\psi^-) - d - R^- \frac{\partial R^-}{\partial z}\right\} / r R^- \sin(\psi^-) \quad (A12)$$

List of Figures

Figure (1) The y-directed infinite line source, strength I at (r_s, θ_s) and the field point $P(r, \theta)$ in the whole-space. Illustrating the acute angle ψ in the propagation triangle OPS for the two cases, $r < r_s$ and $r > r_s$.

Figure (2) The half-space with the plane boundary separating the air $(\sigma_0, \mu_0, \epsilon_0)$ and the earth $(\sigma_1, \mu_0, \epsilon_0)$. with the source $+I(r_s^+, \theta_s^+)$, height H above the interface and image $-I(r_s^-, \theta_s^-)$ distance H below the interface. The propagation triangles for the two sources with the field point on the interface are shown for the cases $r > r_s^+$ and r_s^- .

Figure (3) $H=150\text{m}$, phasors of the average A_n coefficients vs coefficient order for the 5 half-space skin depths 100,250,500,750,1000m, (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (4) $H=150\text{m}$, phasors of the average B_n coefficients vs coefficient order for the 5 skin depths in the half-space (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (5) $H=150\text{m}$, interface x-axis plots of the A_n half-space phasors for each of the 21 orders. This example for the skin depth of 100m. The interface 2000m profile is centred on the source I situated 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (6) $H=150\text{m}$, interface x-axis plots of the B_n half-space phasors for each of the 21 orders. This example for the skin depth of 100m. The interface 2000m profile, sampled at 20m intervals is centred on the source I , at 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (7) $H=150\text{m}$, interface profiles of the $E_y^0 = E_y^p + E_y^s$ (boxes) and $E_y^1 = E_y^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 half-space skin depths of 100,250,500,750,1000m. For the 2000m profile centred on the source I at height 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (8) $H=150\text{m}$, interface profiles of the $H_x^0 = H_x^p + H_x^s$ (boxes) and $H_x^1 = H_x^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 half-space skin depths. For the 2000m profile centred on the source I at height 150m above the interface. (a) modulus (log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (9) $H=150\text{m}$, interface profiles of the $H_z^0 = H_z^p + H_z^s$ (boxes) and $H_z^1 = H_z^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space. For the 2000m profile centred on the source I at height 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (10) The circular cylinder, radius a , in the conducting half-space and centred at the origin O of coordinates. The wave from source $I(r_s, \theta_s)$ is reflected on the cylinder at $Q(a, \theta_t)$ and represented by the image $I'(r_{s'}, \angle XOI')$. In applying the boundary conditions for the cylinder at Q the propagation triangle is OQI' with the acute angle ψ_c either α or $\angle OI'Q = \beta_3$ according

as $r_{s'} < a$ or $r_{s'} > a$.

Figure (11) Source I on the surface at $x = 1500m$ and with the 2000m x-axis surface profile centred on the origin of coordinates. Phasors of the A_n coefficients for the 5 half-space skin depths averaged over the surface profile vs the order of the 21 coefficients. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (12) Source I on the surface, phasors of the B_n coefficients for the 5 half-space skin depths averaged over x-axis surface profile vs the order of the 21 coefficients. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (13) Source I on the surface, phasors of the A_n coefficients, skin depth=100m, vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$ and computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (14) Source I on the surface, phasors of the B_n coefficients, skin depth=100m vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$, computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (15) Source I on the surface, phasors of the $Ey^0 = E_y^p + E_y^s$ (boxes) and $Ey^1 = E_y^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$, computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (16) Source I on the surface, phasors of the $Hx^0 = H_x^p + H_x^s$ (boxes) and $Hx^1 = H_x^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$ computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (17) Source I on the surface, phasors of the $H_z^0 = H_z^p + H_z^s$ (boxes) and $H_z^1 = H_z^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$ computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (18) Phasors of the C_n cylinder coefficients averaged over the 100 20m intervals of the surface profile with coefficient order as abscissa. The numbers 1-5 correspond to each of the five skin depths in the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (19) Phasors of the D_n cylinder coefficients averaged over the 100 20m intervals of the surface profile with coefficient order as abscissa. The numbers 1-5 correspond to the 5 skin depths in the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (20) Phasors of the C_n cylinder coefficients for the particular case of the half-space skin depth=100m and a cylinder skin depth=0.2516m with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (21) Phasors of the Dn cylinder coefficients for the particular case of the half-space skin depth=100m and the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (22) Phasors of $E_y^p + E_y^s$ (boxes) and E_y^t (circles) on the cylinder for the half-space skin depth of 100m and the 5 skin depths in the cylinder. Results are plotted with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa.

Figure (23) Phasors of the $H_\theta^p + H_\theta^s$ (boxes) and H_θ^t (circles) fields on the cylinder for the half-space skin depth of 100m and the 5 skin depths in the cylinder. Results are plotted with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa.

Figure (24) Cylinder in the half-space. Total E_y^0 (boxes) and E_y^1 (circles) fields on the interface for the 5 half-space skin depths and with the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m . For the 2000m surface profile centred on the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (25) Cylinder in the half-space. Total H_x^0 (boxes) and H_x^1 (circles) fields on the interface for the 5 half-space skin depths and with the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m. For the 2000m surface profile centred on the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure (26) Cylinder in the half-space. Total H_z^0 (boxes) and H_z^1 (circles) fields on the interface for the 5 half-space skin depths and with the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m. For the 2000m surface profile centred on the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

FIGURES on following pages.

Figure 1: The y-directed infinite line source, strength I at $S(r_s, \theta_s)$ and the field point $P(r, \theta)$ in the whole-space. Illustrating the acute angle ψ in the propagation triangle OPS for the two cases, $r < r_s$ and $r > r_s$.

Figure 2: The half-space with the plane boundary separating the air ($\sigma_0, \mu_0, \epsilon_0$) and the earth ($\sigma_1, \mu_0, \epsilon_0$). with the source $+I(r_s^+, \theta_s^+)$, height H above the interface and image $-I(r_s^-, \theta_s^-)$ distance H below the interface. The propagation triangles for the two sources with the field point on the interface are shown for the cases $r > r_s^+$ and r_s^- .

Figure 3: $H=150\text{m}$, phasors of the average A_n coefficients vs coefficient order for the 5 half-space skin depths 100,250,500,750,1000m. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 4: $H=150\text{m}$, phasors of the average B_n coefficients vs coefficient order for the 5 skin depths in the half-space. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 5: $H=150m$, interface x-axis plots of the A_n half-space phasors for each of the 21 orders. This example for the skin depth of 100m. The interface 2000m profile is centred on the source I situated 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 6: $H=150\text{m}$, interface x-axis plots of the B_n half-space phasors for each of the 21 orders. This example for the skin depth of 100m. The interface 2000m profile, sampled at 20m intervals is centred on the source I, at 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 7: H=150m, interface profiles of the $E_y^0 = E_y^p + E_y^s$ (boxes) and $E_y^1 = E_y^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 half-space skin depths of 100,250,500,750,1000m. For the 2000m profile centred on the source I at height 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 8: H=150m, interface profiles of the $H_x^0 = H_x^p + H_x^s$ (boxes) and $H_x^1 = H_x^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 half-space skin depths. For the 2000m profile centred on the source I at height 150m above the interface. (a) modulus (log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 9: H=150m, interface profiles of the $H_z^0 = H_z^p + H_z^s$ (boxes) and $H_z^1 = H_z^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space. For the 2000m profile centred on the source I at height 150m above the interface. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 10: The circular cylinder, radius a , in the conducting half-space and centred at the origin O of coordinates. The wave from source $I(r_s, \theta_s)$ is reflected on the cylinder at $Q(a, \theta_t)$ and represented by the image $I'(r_{s'}, \angle XO I')$. In applying the boundary conditions for the cylinder at Q the propagation triangle is OQI' with the acute angle ψ_c either α or $\angle OI'Q$ according as $r_{s'} < a$ or $r_{s'} > a$.

Figure 11: Source I on the surface at $x = 1500m$ and with the 2000m x-axis surface profile centred on the origin of coordinates. Phasors of the A_n coefficients for the 5 half-space skin depths averaged over the surface profile vs the order of the 21 coefficients. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 12: Source I on the surface,phasors of the B_n coefficients for the 5 half-space skin depths averaged over x-axis surface profile vs the order of the 21 coefficients. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 13: Source I on the surface,phasors of the A_n coefficients,skin depth=100m,vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$ and computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 14: Source I on the surface,phasors of the B_n coefficients,skin depth=100m vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$, computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 15: Source I on the surface, phasors of the $Ey^0 = E_y^p + E_y^s$ (boxes) and $Ey^1 = E_y^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$, computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 16: Source I on the surface,phasors of the $Hx^0 = H_x^p + H_x^s$ (boxes) and $Hx^1 = H_x^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$ computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 17: Source I on the surface,phasors of the $H_z^0 = H_z^p + H_z^s$ (boxes) and $H_z^1 = H_z^t$ (circles) fields for the 5 skin depths of the half-space vs the 2000m surface profile with centre at $x = 0$ computed at 20m intervals. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

(a)

(b)

Figure 18: Phasors of the C_n cylinder coefficients averaged over the 100 20m intervals of the surface profile with coefficient order as abscissa. The numbers 1-5 correspond to each of the five skin depths in the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 19: Phasors of the D_n cylinder coefficients averaged over the 100 20m intervals of the surface profile with coefficient order as abscissa. The numbers 1-5 correspond to the 5 skin depths in the cylinder. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 20: Phasors of the C_n cylinder coefficients for the particular case of the half-space skin depth=100m and a cylinder skin depth=0.02516m with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa. (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 21: Phasors of the D_n cylinder coefficients for the particular case of the half-space skin depth=100m and the cylinder skin depth=0.02516m with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa, (a) modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 22: Phasors of $E_y^p + E_y^s$ (boxes) and E_y^t (circles) on the cylinder for the half-space skin depth of 100m and the 5 skin depths in the cylinder. Results are plotted with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa.

Figure 23: Phasors of the $H_{\theta}^p + H_{\theta}^s$ (boxes) and H_{θ}^t (circles) fields on the cylinder for the half-space skin depth of 100m and the 5 skin depths in the cylinder. Results are plotted with the x-axis surface profile as abscissa.

Figure 24: Cylinder in the half-space. Total E_y^0 (boxes) and E_y^1 (circles) fields on the interface for the 5 half-space skin depths and with the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m .For the 2000m surface profile centred on the cylinder. (a)modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 25: Cylinder in the half-space. Total H_x^0 (boxes) and H_x^1 (circles) fields on the interface for the 5 half-space skin depths and with the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m .For the 2000m surface profile centred on the cylinder. (a)modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).

Figure 26: Cylinder in the half-space. Total H_z^0 (boxes) and H_z^1 (circles) fields on the interface for the 5 half-space skin depths and with the cylinder skin depth=0.2516m .For the 2000m surface profile centred on the cylinder. (a)modulus(log), (b) phase(radians).